

COMPARATIVE TESTING OF 433 MHZ RADIO TRANSMITTERS AND RECEIVERS FOR IoT SYSTEMS

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Abstract. This article presents an analysis of RF modules operating at a frequency of 433 MHz, aimed at identifying the most effective combinations of transmitters and receivers in terms of communication range. The experiment involved six types of transmitters and six types of receivers. The results are summarized in a comparative table that reflects the maximum reliable communication distance. The most and least efficient combinations are identified, and conclusions are drawn for practical applications in wireless data transmission systems.

Keywords: RF module, wireless technologies, microcontroller, Arduino, IoT, ISM band, 433 MHz, radio communication, transmission range

Introduction

In today's world, wireless technologies are widely used across various fields — from household devices to industrial and IoT systems [1,2]. The 433 MHz frequency band is a popular choice for short- and medium-range data transmission due to its availability and ease of implementation [3]. The market offers a wide range of modules operating at this frequency, but their performance characteristics and communication ranges can vary significantly. Selecting the right combination of transmitter and receiver can greatly improve the reliability of the connection.

Methodology

The aim of this study is to identify the optimal combination of RF transmitter and receiver modules operating in the 433 MHz band based on the criterion of maximum stable transmission distance. As part of this study, the characteristics of RF modules from various manufacturers were evaluated. All modules were tested under identical conditions — connected to a microcontroller responsible for handling the transmission and reception of signals, as well as to an LCD display that showed the transmitted and received data, enabling visual monitoring of communication accuracy. RF modules are compact devices that integrate various components required for transmitting and receiving radio signals (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Block diagram of an RF module

These modules can operate at various frequencies and utilize different standards, technologies, and radio protocols to transmit information via radio waves [4]. RF modules can be categorized into three main types, depending on the data transmission technology they use [5-6]:

- RF modules with proprietary data transmission technology;
- RF modules that use existing data transmission technologies;
- Simple RF modules without proprietary data transmission technology.

Modules of the first type implement their own communication protocols and signal modulation methods, specifically developed for them. Examples include LoRa, Zigbee, and other specialized RF modules. Modules of the second type rely on established communication standards and protocols such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, GSM/GPRS, and others. They provide a convenient way to integrate wireless communication into devices without the need to develop custom protocols.

Radio modules of the third type provide basic means for wireless communication without the use of complex protocols and technologies. They can operate based on simple modulation methods such as ASK, OOK, FSK, GFSK, and are typically used in simple short-range wireless systems. The main difference between the first two types of radio modules and the third type is that the first two are usually transceivers-devices capable of functioning both as a transmitter and a receiver-whereas third-type radio modules can be implemented either as transmitters or receivers.

Below are the technical specifications of transmitters (see Table 1) and receivers (see Table 2) [6-10]. All radio modules listed in Tables 1 and 2 operate in the ISM frequency bands.

Table 1.

Technical Specifications of Transmitters.

Transmitters						
Radio module	Supply voltage, [V]	Operating frequency, [MHz]	Current consumption, [mA]	Transmitter output power, [db]	Modulation type	Dimensions, [mm]
FS1000A	3-12	433	8	10	ASK	19 x 19 x 7
H34A	2.6-12	433	3.5	15 при 12 В	ASK	10 x 10 x 3
SYN115	1.8-3.6	433.92	12.5	10	ASK /OOK	15 x 12 x 3
STX882	1.2-6	433.92	34	15 при 3 В	ASK /OOK	12 x 15 x 6
WLC-TX1	1.3 -9V	433.92	135 при 9В	17 при 9 В	ASK	11 x 15 x3
WL102-341	2.0V-3.6V	433.92	17	11	ASK /OOK	16 x 12 x 1

Results and discussion

For the experiment, six models of radio transmitters (H34A, SYN115, STX882, WLC-TX1, WL102-341, FS1000A) and six models of radio receivers (H5V4D, SYN480R, SRX882, LR45B, WL101-341, RXB22/RXB12), operating in the 433 MHz range, were used. Each transmitter was tested sequentially paired with each receiver.

Table 2.

Technical Specifications of Receivers.

Receivers						
Radio module	Supply voltage, [V]	Operating frequency, [MHz]	Current consumption, [mA]	Receiver sensitivity [dBm]	Modulation type	Dimensions, [mm]
MX-RM-5V	5	433	4,5	-106...-110	ASK	30 x 13 x 9
H5V4D	5	433	1	-105	ASK	12 x18 x 2
SYN480R	3.3–5.5	433.92	4.5	-107	ASK /OOK	17 x 12 x 5
SRX882	2.4–5.5	433.92	2.8	-110	ASK /OOK	15 x 12 x 6
LR45B	4.5 –5.5	433,92	3~5	-112	ASK	22 x 9 x 3
WL101-341	3.0–3.6	433.92	6.5	-108	ASK /OOK	30 x 9 x 1
RXB12	3.3–5.5	433.92	3.8~4.1	-115	ASK /OOK	30 x 8.5 x 5
RXB22	3.3–5.5	433.92	3.8~4.1	-107	ASK /OOK	30 x 8.5 x 5

All modules were connected to Arduino microcontrollers, which provided:

- transmission of an identical byte sequence through the transmitter;
- reception of data from the radio receiver and comparison of the received information with the reference;

- display of the transmission status (success/error) on an LCD screen.

- Experiment conditions:

Open area without direct radio interference and obstacles.

- Antennas of identical length (17.3 cm — quarter wavelength).
- Format of transmitted data: 16-byte string.
- Retransmission every 2 seconds.
- Recording the distance at which transmission begins to systematically degrade.

For each pair, the maximum distance at which 100% of transmitted messages were successfully received and displayed on the LCD without errors was measured. If reception became unstable, that distance was considered the limit.

The obtained data were systematized in Table 3 and visualized using histograms (Fig. 2) to evaluate the performance of different combinations.

Table 3.

	H5V4D	SYN480R	SRX882	LR45B	WL101-341	RXB22/RXB12
H34A	1	15	2	15	15	30
SYN115	1	15	2	15	15	25
STX882	2	40	35	40	55	50
WLC-TX1	2	40	30	40	50	50

WL102-341	2	40	25	40	40	20
FS1000A	2	40	20	35	40	20

Figure 2. Comparison of communication range of receivers with different transmitters.

Conclusion

Based on the obtained data, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The best results were achieved using STX882, WLC-TX1, and FS1000A transmitters combined with RXB22/RXB12 and WL101-341 receivers. The range of stable transmission in these configurations reached 50–55 meters.

- Average performance (25–40 meters) was demonstrated by SYN480R, SRX882, and LR45B receivers, especially when paired with powerful transmitters.

- The worst results were shown by budget solutions H34A, SYN115, and especially the H5V4D receiver, whose range did not exceed 1–2 meters. Such modules are unsuitable for reliable communication even at short distances.

- The use of an LCD display in conjunction with the microcontroller simplified the debugging and evaluation process, eliminating the need for a PC and external analyzers.

Thus, the obtained data can serve as a practical guideline when choosing radio modules for wireless projects based on Arduino, ESP, or similar microcontrollers. The choice of receiver has no less influence on the communication range and stability than the transmitter itself.

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